

1 **Reproductive fluids, commercial media and organoids: bridging the gap in IVF culture**
2 **systems**

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4 **Running title:** Toward biomimetic embryo culture

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25 **Abstract**

26

27 **BACKGROUND:** Although assisted reproductive technologies (ART) have enabled millions of
28 births worldwide, *in vitro* embryo culture systems remain a simplified and static approximation
29 of the highly dynamic environment of the female reproductive tract. Commercial culture media
30 lack many of the biochemical, biophysical and temporal features of oviductal and uterine fluids,
31 including hormonally regulated secretions, extracellular vesicles and epithelial-derived signalling
32 cues. These limitations are increasingly linked to altered embryonic programming, suboptimal
33 implantation, and subtle but persistent effects on perinatal and long-term health outcomes.

34 **OBJECTIVE AND RATIONALE:** This review critically examines how reproductive tract-
35 derived factors and advanced three-dimensional (3D) *in vitro* models can improve the
36 physiological relevance of embryo culture systems in human ART. We focus on the biological
37 roles of native reproductive fluids and extracellular vesicles, and the emerging contribution of
38 reproductive tract organoids and assembloids as sources of defined, stage-specific secretomes
39 capable of bridging the gap between artificial and *in vivo*-like conditions.

40 **SEARCH METHODS:** A comprehensive literature search was conducted in PubMed, Scopus
41 and Web of Science for studies published up to March 2026 using terms related to embryo culture
42 media, reproductive fluids, extracellular vesicles, organoids, implantation and human IVF.
43 Evidence from human studies and relevant animal models was included to provide mechanistic
44 insight and translational context, with emphasis on experimental approaches directly informing
45 ART practice.

46 **OUTCOMES:** Reproductive tract fluids contain complex mixtures of proteins, metabolites,
47 lipids and extracellular vesicles that regulate fertilization, early embryonic development,
48 epigenetic programming and maternal–embryo communication. While supplementation of
49 embryo culture media with native fluids improves embryo quality and developmental competence
50 in multiple species, clinical translation is constrained by donor variability, biosafety concerns and
51 limited standardization.

52 Reproductive tract 3D cell cultures represent a promising complementary approach, as they can
53 recapitulate key aspects of epithelial architecture, hormonal responsiveness and secretory activity
54 under controlled conditions. Organoid-derived secretomes, including extracellular vesicle
55 cargoes, have been shown to support reproductive processes such as sperm viability, trophoblast
56 function, immune modulation and endometrial receptivity. Moreover, advances in epithelial–
57 stromal assembloids and microengineered platforms further enhance physiological fidelity by
58 partially restoring multicellular interactions relevant to implantation-related signalling.

59 However, these systems also present important limitations, including variability between lines,
60 incomplete cellular complexity, scalability challenges, and unresolved regulatory considerations
61 for clinical translation.

62 **LIMITATIONS, REASONS FOR CAUTION:** This review is based on heterogeneous evidence
63 derived from both human and animal studies, which may limit direct clinical translation due to
64 species-specific differences in reproductive physiology and embryo development. Variability in
65 experimental design, culture conditions and reporting standards across studies introduces
66 potential bias and complicates comparative interpretation. In particular, the use of reproductive
67 fluids is subject to significant inter- and intra-donor variability, differences in collection and
68 processing methods, and incomplete biochemical characterization, all of which represent
69 important confounding factors. Similarly, organoid and assembloid models exhibit variability
70 between lines, incomplete cellular complexity, and differences in differentiation state, which may
71 influence secretome composition and functional outcomes. Moreover, many studies have relied
72 on surrogate endpoints such as embryo morphology or blastocyst formation rather than long-term
73 clinical outcomes, limiting conclusions regarding safety and efficacy in human ART.

74 **WIDER IMPLICATIONS:** Organoid- and assembloid-derived secretomes represent a scalable,
75 ethically sustainable, and mechanistically tractable strategy to advance biomimetic embryo
76 culture in human ART. These systems provide a framework for defining biologically relevant
77 secretory profiles, enabling stage-specific and, potentially, patient-informed supplementation
78 strategies. Integrating reproductive tract organoid technologies with extracellular vesicle biology
79 and dynamic culture platforms may ultimately improve embryo competence, implantation success

80 and long-term offspring health, while supporting safer and more physiologically informed ART
81 practices.

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89

90 **Key words:** assisted reproductive technologies, embryo culture media, human IVF,
91 reproductive fluids, endometrial organoids, oviductal organoids, extracellular vesicles,
92 endometrial receptivity, implantation failure, biomimetic systems

93

94 **WHAT DOES THIS MEAN FOR PATIENTS?**

95 *In vitro* fertilization (IVF) has helped millions of people have children, but embryos are grown in
96 laboratory conditions that do not fully match the natural environment inside the body. In the
97 female reproductive tract, early embryos are exposed to a complex and changing mix of fluids
98 and signals that support their development. Current IVF culture systems cannot fully reproduce
99 these conditions.

100 This review describes new approaches to make embryo culture more similar to natural conditions.

101 One strategy is to use components from reproductive fluids, which contain important molecules
102 that guide early development. Another approach uses advanced laboratory models, called
103 organoids, which are small three-dimensional tissue structures that can produce these supportive
104 factors in a controlled way.

105 These innovations may improve embryo development, implantation, and pregnancy outcomes,
106 and could support healthier babies. However, further research is needed to confirm their safety
107 and effectiveness before they can be widely used in clinical practice.

108

109

110 **Introduction**

111 Current IVF culture systems support acceptable early embryo development but fail to reproduce
112 the dynamic biochemical, mechanical and temporal cues of the reproductive tract (Sciorio and
113 Rinaudo, 2023). *In vivo*, preimplantation embryos are exposed to a continuously changing
114 environment shaped by epithelial secretions, mucins, glycoproteins, extracellular vesicles (EVs),
115 epithelium activity, fluid flow and hormonal oscillations (Godakumara *et al.*, 2023; Kölle *et al.*,
116 2009). These factors regulate metabolic activity, epigenetic remodelling, developmental timing
117 and embryo–maternal communication (Pavličev *et al.*, 2017). In contrast, *in vitro* culture (IVC)
118 media still rely on static media that lack many of these features, offering only a partial
119 approximation of physiological conditions (Cairo Consensus Group, 2020)

120 These discrepancies between *in vivo* and *in vitro* conditions contribute to measurable differences
121 in metabolic programming, transcriptional profiles, and fetal growth trajectories between *in vivo*-
122 and *in vitro*-derived conceptuses (Aksu *et al.*, 2012; Driver *et al.*, 2012). Such limitations
123 underscore the need for more biomimetic culture systems capable of integrating essential
124 biochemical and biophysical properties of reproductive tract fluids. Advances in reproductive
125 tract organoids and assembloids, and their secretome, now provide new opportunities to generate
126 defined, reproducible and physiologically relevant supplements that may overcome the
127 constraints associated with native reproductive fluids.

128 This review synthesizes the current evidence on reproductive fluids, commercial media, and 3D
129 cell culture-derived factors, highlighting conceptual advances, methodological limitations and the
130 translational challenges of implementing physiologically inspired culture systems.

131

132 **Culture media: current performance and intrinsic limitations**

133 Assisted reproductive technologies (ART) have resulted in more than ten million births since
134 1978 (Adamson *et al.*, 2025; Baker *et al.*, 2025; Edwards *et al.*, 1969, 1970). Contemporary
135 culture media incorporate salts, carbohydrates, amino acids, buffers and protein supplements, but
136 lack many critical components and physical properties characteristic of reproductive tract fluids
137 (Sunde *et al.*, 2016; Zagers *et al.*, 2025).

138 Since the earliest mammalian media (e.g. Earle's, Bavister's, Waymouth's, Whittingham's),
139 human embryo culture formulations have been progressively refined into modern sequential and
140 single-step systems (Edwards et al., 1970; Morbeck et al., 2017; Zagers et al., 2025). Yet no
141 consensus exists on a superior medium and reported differences in clinical or laboratory outcomes
142 are often modest and inconsistent. Meaningful comparison is further hampered by proprietary
143 compositions, divergent protein supplements, variable oxygen tension and non-standardized
144 laboratory practices, which together limit mechanistic interpretation (Sciorio and Rinaudo, 2023).
145 Contemporary media are broadly categorized as chemically defined or undefined, depending on
146 their protein source. Defined formulations offer greater reproducibility and quality control,
147 whereas undefined supplements, such as serum or reproductive fluids, introduce inter- and intra-
148 donor variability that complicates standardization. In general, commercial media combine
149 inorganic salts, carbohydrates, amino acids, buffers and protein supplements, with optional
150 additions such as antibiotics, vitamins and chelators (Table 1). However, the precise contribution
151 of individual components to embryo competence remains difficult to disentangle, and authors
152 have therefore called for full transparency in media composition and patient cohorts (Sunde et al.,
153 2016; Tarahomi et al., 2019; Zagers et al., 2025). Even under optimized conditions, these
154 formulations force embryos to adapt to an artificial environment, and to activate metabolic and
155 molecular stress responses to maintain development *in vitro* (Lee et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2025).
156

157 **The influence of culture media on embryonic programming**

158 Embryo culture medium performance is commonly evaluated based on early developmental
159 parameters, like cleavage rate, cell division kinetics and blastocyst formation. However,
160 implantation and gestational success, typically measured by live birth rate, remain the most
161 meaningful clinical endpoint (Gnoth et al., 2011). The period of *in vitro* embryo culture coincides
162 with the global epigenetic reprogramming of the pre-implantation embryo (Zhu et al., 2018). This
163 developmental window is therefore considered particularly sensitive to environmental influences.
164 Despite this biological susceptibility, relatively few studies have directly assessed the specific
165 impact of culture media on the epigenome of embryos and extraembryonic tissues.

166 So far, the direct effect of *in vitro* culture conditions on placental DNA methylation (DNAm) is
167 modest and inconsistent across cohorts, with only a limited number of recurrent candidate loci.
168 Analysis on umbilical cord blood (UCB) from neonates conceived under different culture media
169 (G5, Vitrolife; human tubal fluid medium, HTF, Lonza) shows no differences in DNAm between
170 media groups (Koeck *et al.*, 2022). However, when UCB was ART-conceived newborns is
171 compared with that of naturally conceived newborns, global DNA hypomethylation was observed
172 (Håberg *et al.*, 2022). Similarly, ART-derived term placentas exhibit less DNAm at imprinted
173 loci such as the *PEG1/MEST* region (Barberet *et al.*, 2022; Nelissen *et al.*, 2013), alongside
174 downregulation of TRIM28, a key stabilizer of genomic imprinting (Auvinen *et al.*, 2024).
175 Beyond methylation patterns, transcriptomic analyses indicate that ART-associated placental
176 changes are enriched in pathways related to hormonal regulation, insulin secretion and vascular
177 development, particularly through downregulation of *NOTCH3* and *DLK1* genes (Auvinen *et al.*,
178 2024). Whether these molecular signatures directly translate into apparent structural placental
179 abnormalities, such as accelerated villous maturation, placenta praevia, placental abruption or
180 placenta accreta spectrum, remains ambiguous (Londero *et al.*, 2021; Matsuzaki *et al.*, 2021;
181 Vermey *et al.*, 2019).
182 Clinically, although children conceived through ART are generally healthy, the aforementioned
183 molecular findings, together with epidemiological evidence, offer a plausible mechanistic link of
184 ART with an increased risk of cardiometabolic and vascular disorders, imprinting disorders,
185 preeclampsia, hypertensive complications of pregnancy, and low birth weight (Auvinen *et al.*,
186 2024; Cui *et al.*, 2020; Pinborg *et al.*, 2023; Qin *et al.*, 2017). Birth weight, as a representative
187 outcome, reflects a complex interplay of parental, embryological and genetic determinants.
188 Within this multifactorial framework, growing evidence suggests that embryo culture media
189 formulation and culture strategy may contribute measurably to perinatal growth patterns, even if
190 their molecular effects are subtle and context-dependent (Ahlström *et al.*, 2023; Li *et al.*, 2025;
191 Sonigo *et al.*, 2024).
192 For instance, independent and randomized studies comparing human embryo culture mediums,
193 including G1.3, G5, G5-plus (Vitrolife) and human tubal fluid (HTF) versus K-SICM (Cook)

194 medium showed that singletons cultured using Vitrolife and HTF mediums had higher birth
195 weights (Dumoulin *et al.*, 2010; Li *et al.*, 2025). In fact, Vitrolife vs Cook culture medium growth
196 differences persisted through the first two years of life, highlighting how subtle differences in
197 media composition can have lasting postnatal effects (Kleijkers *et al.*, 2014). Further examples
198 include mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) variants, which in naturally-conceived (NC) individuals
199 are associated with body weight (Flaquer *et al.*, 2014). This relationship appears only partially
200 preserved in ART cohorts, as an enrichment of de novo mtDNA mutations (particularly non-
201 synonymous and rRNA variants, also present in NC groups) seems to be magnified in ART
202 populations, with additional influence from maternal age, ovarian stimulation and *in vitro* culture-
203 related factors (Mertens *et al.*, 2024). In this case, exposure to Cook or UZB (an in-house medium
204 made in the UZ Brussel) embryo culture medium appears to override the effect of mtDNA
205 variation on fetal growth, whereas embryos cultured in Vitrolife medium show similar patterns to
206 those of the NC groups (Mertens *et al.*, 2024).

207 Importantly, current findings underscore that ART-associated molecular signatures are not yet
208 universal but vary across the populations, study designs and developmental stages assessed. The
209 lack of standardization in procedural variables (e.g., media type, oxygen conditions, IVF/ICSI
210 embryo transfer protocols) across clinics and even within the same institution creates
211 inconsistencies that can mask subtle biological effects and challenge the interpretation of
212 comparative analyses (Racowsky *et al.*, 2025). These limitations also reinforce the broader
213 conceptual shift required in the field: moving beyond merely “supportive” culture environments
214 toward culture systems that are actively biomimetic, capable of recapitulating the biochemical,
215 biophysical and temporal complexity of the reproductive tract.

216 This focus is increasingly driving interest in the use of reproductive-fluid supplementation,
217 dynamic co-culture platforms, and organoid or assembloids derived secretomes, all of which aim
218 to reintroduce aspects of the physiological niche into embryo culture. Their integration with 3D-
219 cell culture models and embryo co-culture models represents a key frontier in constructing more
220 faithful reproductive microenvironments, and insights from these platforms will likely inform the
221 next generation of biomimetic media.

222

223 Reproductive fluids as biomimetic additives: a model for optimized media?

224 Replicating the *in vivo* environment in *in vitro* embryo culture is by far more than a simple
225 combination of salts, energy substrates and amino acids (Figure 1). Modern approaches
226 emphasize the need to adapt the composition of the culture media to the specific metabolic and
227 developmental needs of the embryo at each stage. This includes not only adjusting inorganic
228 elements but also incorporating a wide range of organic compounds (vitamins, lipids, growth
229 factors and antioxidants), many of which are naturally present in oviductal and uterine fluids
230 (Table 2). Analyses of human oviductal fluid revealed substantial discrepancies in amino acids,
231 energy substrates and ionic composition when compared with conventional media, supporting the
232 development of oviduct-inspired formulations such as OVIT (Utsunomiya *et al.*, 2022).

233 Supplementation of media for *in vitro* oocyte maturation, fertilization and embryo culture may
234 serve as a foundation for next-generation approaches aimed at biomimicking natural reproductive
235 fluids (Canovas *et al.*, 2017; París-Oller *et al.*, 2021), although their ability to emulate the
236 biochemical and physical conditions of the oviduct and uterus remains limited. *In vivo*, embryos
237 experience a dynamic microenvironment characterized not only by temporally regulated nutrient
238 concentrations but also by fluid flow, ciliary movement, mucus-rich secretions, and complex
239 interactions with epithelial surfaces (Coy *et al.*, 2012). Current culture media compensate only
240 partially for these attributes, often lacking immunoregulatory glycoproteins, cytokines,
241 extracellular vesicles, and the dynamic fluctuations of ions and amino acid profiles that
242 characterize the *in vivo* uterine environment (Zagers *et al.*, 2025).

243 Reproductive tract fluids contain thousands of components, including proteins, glycoproteins,
244 lipids, metabolites, extracellular vesicles, cytokines, miRNA and hormones, that contribute to the
245 embryo's natural microenvironment (Apostolov *et al.*, 2025; Gonella-Diaza *et al.*, 2024; Li *et al.*,
246 2023a; Piibor *et al.*, 2023). Unsurprisingly, numerous studies have explored the use of
247 reproductive fluids or their derivatives as supplements to the medium as a strategy to improve
248 biomimicry *in vitro* (Canovas *et al.*, 2017; París-Oller *et al.*, 2021). Studies in livestock
249 demonstrate that reproductive fluids can influence fertilization, cleavage, gene expression,

250 metabolic activity, placental vascularization and pregnancy rates, although outcomes vary
251 markedly across species, experimental conditions and fluid origin (Heras, Soriano-Ubeda, *et al.*,
252 2025; París-Oller *et al.*, 2022; Párraga-Ros *et al.*, 2023). These inconsistencies highlight both the
253 promise and the complexity of using native physiological secretions to support embryo
254 development.

255

256 **Oviductal and uterine reproductive fluids in embryo culture**

257 Oviductal fluid (OF) provides a dynamic milieu shaped by ciliary activity, epithelial secretion
258 and endocrine fluctuations. Before fertilization, OF undergoes key modifications that facilitate
259 gamete interaction and fertilization, e.g., oviduct-specific glycoprotein (OVGP1) promotes zona
260 pellucida hardening in polyspermy-prone species such as pigs and goats, thereby reducing
261 fertilization anomalies (Bragança *et al.*, 2021; Coy *et al.*, 2008). Because preimplantation
262 development naturally spans two distinct environments (the oviduct during cleavage and the
263 uterus during compaction and blastocyst formation), several studies have explored sequential
264 supplementation strategies (Hamdi *et al.*, 2018; Leal *et al.*, 2022; Pakniyat *et al.*, 2025). *In vitro*
265 culture of porcine embryos, first in oviductal fluid (1% v/v) and then in uterine fluid (1% v/v)
266 produced blastocysts that more closely resembled their *in vivo* counterparts in cell number and
267 epigenetic signatures (Canovas *et al.*, 2017; París-Oller *et al.*, 2021). Follow-up analyses in this
268 porcine model revealed that supplementation with reproductive fluids also mitigated aberrant
269 placental gene expression typically associated with *in vitro* embryo production. Placentas derived
270 from embryos cultured with reproductive fluids did not show the increased expression of
271 developmentally relevant genes such as *PEG3* and *LUM*, which were otherwise dysregulated in
272 conventional (IVC) conditions, suggesting that fluid-derived factors contribute to early placental
273 programming with downstream consequences for offspring development (París-Oller *et al.*,
274 2021).

275 Human reproductive fluids (HRFs) collected under well-established quality control protocols
276 demonstrated bioactivity in a bovine embryo assay, with 1% (v/v) supplementation of culture
277 medium supporting high cleavage rates and blastocyst formation. As a subsequent proof-of-

278 concept in this study, embryos cultured with autologous uterine fluid could develop into
279 successful pregnancies in three women, with two of them resulting in healthy live births (Canha-
280 Gouveia *et al.*, 2021).

281 Despite this evidence, responses to reproductive fluids are species-specific and dose-dependent,
282 as excessive concentrations of reproductive fluids can impair development. This is relevant in
283 cattle embryos, where the use of oviductal and uterine fluids during IVC in more than 5% of cases
284 was negative (Hamdi *et al.*, 2018). Similarly, exposure of mouse oocytes/cumulus complexes to
285 ovarian endometriotic fluid led to a significant reduction in the proportion of hatching/hatched
286 blastocysts, even when initial fertilization and cleavage rates were not substantially altered
287 (Piromlertamorn *et al.*, 2013). These findings highlight that defining supplementation merely as
288 a percentage (v/v) may be insufficient, as protein composition and concentration can vary
289 substantially between fluid batches. Future strategies should therefore aim to standardize
290 supplementation based on quantitative characterization of key protein and bioactive component
291 concentrations, enabling tighter control of exposure levels and minimizing the risk of toxicity or
292 developmental perturbations.

293 Overall, reproductive fluids and their bioactive components provide a valuable baseline for
294 designing physiologically relevant culture systems. When incorporated in a controlled and
295 standardized way, these components have the potential to enhance embryo quality and
296 developmental progression, supporting improved outcomes in ART (Heras *et al.*, 2025; Lopes *et al.*,
297 2020; Serrano-Albal *et al.*, 2025). However, the direct use of biological fluids poses potential
298 biosafety risks, including the transmission of infectious agents, inflammatory mediators and
299 immunogenic components. Translating approaches that incorporate reproductive fluids as
300 standard supplements for IVC systems would require addressing stringent safety regulations and
301 donor-screening requirements. Moreover, only a limited number of studies have demonstrated the
302 feasibility of implementing such strategies in a controlled and reproducible manner.

303

304 **Extracellular vesicles: emerging mediators of reproductive communication**

305 Extracellular vesicles (EVs) have been isolated from a wide range of reproductive sources (e.g.,
306 human, murine, livestock), including follicular fluid (FF), ampullary oviduct fluid (AOF), oviduct
307 fluid (OF), uterine fluid (UF), embryo-conditioned media and oviduct epithelial cell cultures,
308 underscoring their central role in maternal–embryo communication (Hamdi et al., 2024; Li et al.,
309 2023; Ma et al., 2022; Muraoka et al., 2024; Pakniyat et al., 2025). These vesicles transport
310 bioactive cargo, such as miRNAs, proteins and membrane receptors, that can be internalized by
311 gametes and embryos, influencing preimplantation development, developmental competence, cell
312 allocation, oxidative balance and implantation-related pathways (Li et al., 2023; Ma et al., 2022).
313 Evidence from animal models further supports their function as dynamic mediators of maternal
314 signaling, modulating embryonic development in a stage, dose and tissue-specific manner. For
315 instance, murine embryos cocultured with varying doses of human fallopian tube-derived EVs
316 (from patients with uterine fibroids) showed improved developmental outcomes, although the
317 effects were not strictly dose-dependent nor consistently linked to a particular donor (Li *et al.*,
318 2023).

319 Consistent with the concept of temporally regulated EV signaling, murine oviduct-derived EVs
320 isolated across estrous stages enhance blastocyst yield, cell number and embryo quality, with the
321 strongest effects in EVs isolated from the diestrus group (representing the highest levels of
322 estrogen receptor, a factor known to support early embryogenesis (Xue *et al.*, 2025). Importantly,
323 when sequential and EV replenishment supplementation was done (particularly on day 3 and 4
324 post-fertilization), an increase in hatching rates was observed. This suggests that EV bioactivity
325 declines in static culture, and temporal renewal more closely mimics the continuous *in vivo*
326 exposure within the reproductive tract (Xue *et al.*, 2025).

327 While isolated studies in bovine have reported that specific EV-associated components, such as
328 miR-146b, present in conditioned culture medium, may exert detrimental effects on embryos
329 (Pavani *et al.*, 2024), the broader body of evidence supports a predominantly beneficial role of
330 reproductive EVs in early development. Studies using medium supplemented with microRNA
331 (miR-378a-3p from embryonic sources) and follicular oviductal- and uterine fluid-derived EVs
332 support an overall increase in blastocyst yield and hatching rates (Benedetti et al., 2024; Hamdi

333 et al., 2018, 2024; Pavani et al., 2022), and furthermore, enhanced the expression of embryo
334 development and implantation-relevant genes such as *IFNT*, the key cytokine required for
335 maternal recognition of pregnancy (Benedetti et al., 2024; Leal et al., 2022).

336 Bovine and murine findings provide a compelling proof of concept, which is further supported by
337 human data in which microRNAs were dysregulated in women with recurrent implantation
338 failure, and were associated with pathways governing endometrial receptivity and implantation
339 competence (Liu, wang, et al., 2021). In this case, endometrial EVs from fertile women improved
340 implantation competence compared with EVs from women experiencing recurrent implantation
341 failure (Liu *et al.*, 2020). These findings support the concept that fluid-derived microRNAs
342 function not only as biomarkers of reproductive outcome but also as integral regulatory signals
343 within the implantation microenvironment.

344

345 **Beyond supplementation: toward automated, dynamic and biomimetic platforms**

346 Early studies showed that the co-culture of human gametes or embryos with reproductive tract
347 epithelial cells enhanced developmental outcomes (Bongso *et al.*, 1989; Yeung *et al.*, 1992).

348 These systems aimed to restore the dynamic, bidirectional communication between the embryo
349 and its maternal environment: interactions that are otherwise absent in conventional static culture.

350 Although traditional co-culture systems are no longer used in routine ART due to advances in
351 next-generation media, they have re-emerged as physiological bioreactors to investigate the
352 maternal–embryo crosstalk, and uncover molecular signals lost in simplified media.

353 This renewed appreciation for the importance of dynamic maternal signaling prompted the
354 development of advanced microfluidic reproductive platforms. Oviduct or uterus-on-a-chip
355 models represent the next conceptual step, offering dynamic control over fluid flow,
356 spatiotemporal gradients, compartmentalization and luminal shear forces (Ahn et al., 2021; Ferraz
357 et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2022), all of which are features impossible to recreate in conventional
358 IVC drops. Dual chamber “endometrium-on-a-chip” devices, for instance, maintain long-term co-
359 culture of stromal and endothelial cells, enabling decidualization patterns while simulating a full
360 28-day hormonal cycle (Gnecco *et al.*, 2017). More recent iterations incorporate epithelial,

361 stromal, endothelial or myometrial compartments in configurations that reproduce the receptivity
362 marker expression and transcriptomic fidelity of native tissue (Ahn *et al.*, 2021b; Busch *et al.*,
363 2024). Collectively, these platforms begin to approximate patient-specific, multi-cellular uterine
364 microenvironments for functional interrogation of embryo–maternal crosstalk (Lee *et al.*, 2025).
365 Although the application of microfluidic systems to clinical ART remains largely exploratory,
366 these technologies outline what the next generation of IVF platforms could become: dynamic,
367 automated and biomimetic. The parallel outset of robotic micromanipulation further illustrates
368 this trajectory. The recent successful births following automated intracytoplasmic sperm injection
369 (ICSI), demonstrate that automated systems can achieve clinical-grade precision, even when
370 operated by individuals without extensive embryology training (Costa-Borges *et al.*, 2023;
371 Mendizabal-Ruiz *et al.*, 2025). The convergence of such robotic technologies and microfluidic
372 culture devices suggests a future in which embryo handling, gamete injection and early
373 development occur within tightly controlled integrated platforms that function simultaneously as
374 culture systems, physiological bioreactors and precision instrumentation. Together, they offer a
375 path toward standardizing embryo culture conditions, mitigating procedural heterogeneity (e.g.,
376 human-handling, lab-specific practices), one of the most significant sources of inconsistency in
377 ART, and enabling the development of universally applicable protocols across laboratories and
378 clinics (Racowsky *et al.*, 2025).

379

380 **Challenges associated with the use of reproductive fluids in ART**

381 Technical limitations, particularly the difficulty of collecting sufficient volumes of oviductal and
382 uterine fluid from individual donors, often necessitate pooling samples, thereby introducing inter-
383 individual variability that may mask specific biological effects. Even in controlled animal models,
384 differences in donor physiology, collection methods, storage conditions and processing pipelines
385 yield fluids with markedly different biochemical profiles and biological effects. Such variability
386 is incompatible with the strict standardization required for human ART. From a regulatory
387 standpoint, reproductive fluids would likely be classified as complex human-derived biological
388 products, necessitating good manufacturing practice (GMP) compliant procurement, pathogen

389 screening, sterility testing, endotoxin validation, and full traceability: requirements that currently
390 lack standardized implementation pathways in ART laboratories.

391 Another unresolved key issue is what the authors mean when they state that a certain percentage
392 of “native” or “physiological” reproductive fluid is added as a supplement to the culture media.
393 These additions are often described only in volumetric terms (e.g., 1–10% fluid supplementation),
394 and the biochemical concentration and composition of the supplemented solution remain
395 unknown. Without defining which molecular components are biologically active, at what
396 effective concentrations, and their functional integrity (e.g. mRNA may degrade rapidly under
397 the culture conditions), researchers cannot determine which molecules mediate the observed
398 effect (Chronopoulou and Harper, 2015). Hence, the field would benefit from the establishment
399 of standardized reporting frameworks requiring biochemical characterization, batch qualification
400 criteria, and absolute molecular quantification before clinical translation.

401 A rational translational pathway may involve deconstructing reproductive fluids into defined
402 molecular components and reconstructing synthetic, quality-controlled mimetics that retain
403 biological functionality while meeting regulatory and safety standards. In this sense, the
404 emergence of three-dimensional tissue cultures and systems offers a captivating alternative. As
405 3D technology continues to evolve, it holds the potential to redefine IVF and IVC systems by
406 providing this biomimetic microenvironment that closely mirrors the *in vivo* reproductive tract,
407 ultimately improving embryo quality and implantation outcomes in a clinically applicable and
408 ethically sustainable manner.

409

410 **Organoids in reproductive research: current advances in 3D *in vitro* models**

411 Organoid technology has revolutionized the study of tissue-specific biology, offering
412 unprecedented opportunities for modeling reproductive tract function *in vitro*. The field was
413 initiated by the seminal work of Sato and Clevers in 2009, who generated self-organizing, stem
414 cell-derived 3D intestinal structures that recapitulate key native features (Sato et al., 2009). This
415 foundational breakthrough paved the way for organoid generation from almost all tissues, from a
416 variety of sources of cell types (embryonic, adult or differentiated cells).

417 Current advances enabled the derivation of oviductal and uterine organoids from a wide range of
418 species, including humans, mice, cattle, pigs and other domestic animals (Bourdon *et al.*, 2021;
419 Thompson *et al.*, 2023). Resembling native epithelia (Figure 2A), these organoids comprise at
420 least two cell types: ciliated and non-ciliated or secretory cells (Boretto *et al.*, 2017; Turco *et al.*,
421 2017). In general, these fundamental traits are critically dependent on active Wnt and Notch
422 signalling pathways (Sato *et al.*, 2011). Accordingly, culture conditions are typically
423 supplemented with growth factors such as epidermal growth factor (EGF), Noggin, and the Wnt
424 agonist R-spondin 1 (RSPO1). Where Wnt signaling (through LGR4/5/6 receptors) maintains
425 epithelial stemness, Notch signaling modulates cell fate, and Noggin prevents premature
426 differentiation (Mahe *et al.*, 2013; Sato *et al.*, 2011).

427 Female reproductive tract organoids can be generated from fresh, cryopreserved biopsies and even
428 menstrual flow samples, reflecting the donor's physiological and genetic background (Bui *et al.*,
429 2020; Cindrova-Davies *et al.*, 2021; Kessler *et al.*, 2015; Kopper *et al.*, 2019; Rizo *et al.*, 2025).
430 These models can be established from tissue representing different cycle phases, including
431 secretory, proliferative, decidual and atrophic endometrium. Once established, organoids grow
432 long-term through the expansion of individual cells (Figure 2B) and acquire a 'conserved'
433 epithelial polarity (the apical or luminal surface is enclosed (apical-in), whereas the basolateral
434 surface faces the outside and interacts with the extracellular matrix (ECM), (basolateral-out)
435 Figure 2C, D) (Boretto *et al.*, 2017; Kessler *et al.*, 2015; Turco *et al.*, 2017). Importantly,
436 organoids secrete a variety of proteins, lipids, metabolites and extracellular vesicles that reflect
437 features of reproductive tract fluid composition, making them attractive candidates for developing
438 next-generation biomimetic culture supplements (Dong *et al.*, 2023; Simintiras *et al.*, 2021).

439

440 **Modelling oviduct and endometrial epithelial function**

441 Despite the importance of the fallopian tube (FT), in-depth investigations have historically been
442 constrained by limited access to primary tissue and the short lifespan of ex vivo epithelial cultures.
443 Fallopian tube organoids (FTOs) overcome these constraints by allowing the formation of
444 polarized epithelia composed of secretory (PAX8⁺) and ciliated acetylated (tubulin⁺) cells,

445 interconnected by tight junctions. FTOs are responsive to physiological concentrations of
446 hormones (estradiol and progesterone), inducing the expression of differentiation markers
447 reflective of reproductive phases and exhibiting minimal transcriptional divergence from native
448 tissue (Kessler *et al.*, 2015). FTOs are also versatile for practical utility, with the apical
449 compartment outperforming commercial media in maintaining human sperm motility and
450 viability for up to 96 hours (Gatimel *et al.*, 2025). This reinforces FTOs as powerful platforms for
451 studying gamete–epithelium interactions, hormone signalling, early fertilization dynamics and
452 disease modelling in a patient-specific context (Yucer *et al.*, 2021).

453 Endometrial organoids (EMOs) emulate, at a certain level, the uterine complexity. EMOs express
454 canonical markers of glandular epithelium (*MUC1*, *E-CADHERIN*, *CK7* and *EPCAM*) (Gnecco
455 *et al.*, 2023) and produce luminal/apical secretions according to hormonal stimulations. Upon
456 exposure to oestradiol, EMOs undergo proliferative expansion, upregulate key genes such as
457 *ESR1*, *TRH*, *MCM2–4* and *OLFM4*, and exhibit pseudostratified glandular morphology
458 characteristic of the *in vivo* proliferative endometrium (Boretto *et al.*, 2017; Turco *et al.*, 2017).
459 Subsequent progesterone treatment induces a secretory phenotype, marked by glandular folding,
460 ciliation and increased mucin production (Figure 3A). This is paralleled by the upregulation of
461 genes associated with secretory differentiation and early pregnancy, including *PAEP*, *SPP1*,
462 *MUC1*, *ALOX15*, *AQP3* and *17βHSD2* (Boretto *et al.*, 2017; Fitzgerald *et al.*, 2023).

463 It is worth mentioning that the use of 3D advanced cultures aligns with the 3Rs framework for
464 animal studies. These models can reduce the number of animals required for validation and refine
465 experimental design by enabling controlled models of hormone response and cell communication.
466 Additionally, because organoids retain donor-specific transcriptional and epigenetic traits, they
467 offer opportunities to investigate individual variability in receptivity and ART outcomes,
468 something that cannot be captured in traditional animal models.

469

470 **Bridging animal models and clinical ART: the emerging role of organoid-derived secretions**

471 High-resolution transcriptomics, proteomics and metabolomics analyses of human organoid-
472 derived secretions (ODS) now enable systematic mapping of epithelial secretory pathways and

473 direct comparisons to *in vivo* fluids across the proliferative, secretory and peri-implantation
474 window (Dong *et al.*, 2023). ODS secreted factors not only provide nutrients, but they also
475 modulate embryo requirements, endometrial receptivity trophoblast invasion, and immunological
476 responses (Salamonsen *et al.*, 2013; Simintiras *et al.*, 2021).

477 When secretions of human EMOs generated under mid-to-late luteal phase hormone stimulation
478 are applied to macrophages, the cells shift their phenotype toward a decidual-like profile,
479 characterized by reduced pro-inflammatory signaling and increased markers of tissue remodeling
480 and tolerance (e.g. CD209, NRP1) (Lin *et al.*, 2023). Extending this argument, metabolites from
481 extraorganoid fluid (EOF) and intraorganoid fluid (IOF) of these EMOs are enriched in metabolic
482 and immunomodulatory molecules, such as hypoxanthine, which is needed for nucleotide
483 synthesis during rapid embryonic cell divisions, and spermine, a polyamine that modulates
484 cytokine balance and facilitates decidualization (Simintiras *et al.*, 2021).

485 Currently, the application of ODS to embryo culture is no longer theoretical. Novel studies
486 employing bovine organoid-derived, cargo-specific oviductal extracellular vesicles, as well as
487 diestrus-phase endometrial ODS (organoids hormonally programmed with estradiol and
488 medroxyprogesterone acetate), have demonstrated their capacity to maintain/improve the quality
489 of *in vitro* produced embryos (Devkota *et al.*, 2025; Menjivar *et al.*, 2025). Importantly, emerging
490 evidence further indicates that ODS derived from hormonally responsive oviductal organoids can
491 also promote sperm capacitation (Navarro-Serna *et al.*, 2026), thereby highlighting their broader
492 role in coordinating gamete–embryo interactions. Metabolomic profiling further supports the
493 physiological relevance of these systems. For instance, the detection of metabolites such as
494 isobutyrylcarnitine (normally present in native bovine uterine fluid) within bovine endometrial
495 intra-organoid fluid (IOF), suggests that ODS recapitulates key aspects of the luminal
496 biochemical milieu. Functionally, although not yet equivalent to synthetic oviductal fluid (SOF)
497 controls, day 7 blastocysts cultured solely in IOF, without the need for a standard commercial
498 culture medium, exhibit prolonged survival, increased hatching rates and enhanced trophectoderm
499 specification by day 10 (Devkota *et al.*, 2025). So far, the results indicate that the intrinsic
500 secretory programs of ODS, particularly when synchronized to relevant hormonal states, can

501 generate a microenvironment that supports embryogenesis more effectively than conventional
502 media.

503

504 **Strengths and current limitations of reproductive tract organoids**

505 Overall, these findings position organoid systems as “secretory bioreactors”, laying the
506 conceptual groundwork for next-generation embryo culture strategies. For this transition to occur,
507 researchers should bear in mind that while organoids successfully reproduce epithelial signaling,
508 they lack the stromal, vascular, immune and endocrine cell interactions present *in vivo*. As a result,
509 their secretomes, though informative, do not fully capture the complexity or dynamic hormonal
510 composition of natural reproductive fluids.

511 The composition of ODS can also shift over time depending on passage number, media
512 formulation, and the degree of cell differentiation. In addition, extracellular matrix scaffolds such
513 as Matrigel (ECM derived from the Engelbreth–Holm–Swarm mouse sarcoma) introduce non-
514 physiological components and limitations for mechanistic and translational studies. All these
515 variables and phenotypic drifts challenge reproducibility and raise questions about whether
516 organoid-derived secretions can be produced with the consistency required for clinical
517 application. Despite the intrinsic variability of ODS, the modularity of organoids remains an
518 attractive proof-of-concept for identifying and characterizing physiological factors under certain
519 *in vitro* conditions. Looking ahead, ODS opens the possibility to adjust them to specific
520 embryonic stages, physiological states (follicular versus luteal phases) or patient-specific
521 biobanks. Achieving clinical applicability does not require eliminating biological variation;
522 rather, it requires defining acceptable ranges and reproducible manufacturing steps, as is done for
523 other complex biological products (e.g., human serum albumin, platelet lysates, conditioned
524 media used in cell therapy).

525 In response to some of these limitations, a scaffold-free endometrial organoid model was
526 generated using low-adhesion agarose micromoulds to produce apical-out (AO) spheroids with
527 an epithelial perimeter and stromal core (Figure 3A) (Wiwatpanit *et al.*, 2020). Although
528 originally designed to study polycystic ovary syndrome, its apical-out architecture provides an

529 accessible luminal interface (Figure 3A and C), offering a unique opportunity to directly expose
530 gametes or embryos to native apical secretions. Similarly, AO-EMOs incorporating stromal and
531 endothelial cells allow secretions from the internal gland-like epithelial cells to diffuse to the
532 exterior (Figure 3C), thereby modulating cell behaviour in ways consistent with early pregnancy,
533 as happens when they are co-cultured with human blastocysts or their *in vitro* counterparts:
534 derived blastoids (Shibata *et al.*, 2024).

535

536 **Roadmap to target ODS in translational ART media supplements**

537 At present, we lack standardized benchmarks to define what an “optimal” or “physiologically
538 relevant” organoid secretome should look like. Moreover, it remains unclear whether all
539 components of these secretions (e.g., mRNAs, signaling proteins, redox enzymes, EV-associated
540 factors) retain their biological activity throughout the entire *in vitro* culture period, or whether
541 some undergo degradation or inactivation. Addressing these issues will require parallel
542 phenotypic and molecular characterization of organoids (e.g., transcriptomic markers of
543 differentiation state) alongside quantitative proteomic/EV profiling of their secretions.

544 Knowing which molecules are necessary and sufficient to recapitulate the beneficial effects of
545 native reproductive fluids requires a systematic fractionation and functional testing of individual
546 groups of molecules (proteins, lipids, metabolites and EV-associated cargo). Following this,
547 establishing a standard protocol and sample origin/use among laboratories, and determining the
548 optimal concentration ranges for secreted factors, are crucial parameters that should be evaluated
549 hereafter. Studies must also be accompanied by new quality control pipelines, including
550 functional assays (such as embryo developmental kinetics, zona pellucida remodeling or
551 metabolic readouts), which are essential for determining potency rather than simply relying on
552 the presence or absence of factors.

553 A practical intermediate step would be to evaluate these secretomes in well-established model
554 systems, such as mouse or bovine, where developmental endpoints and embryo competence are
555 routinely measured, and where ethical and logistical barriers are comparatively lower. Moreover,
556 the recent development of human blastoids and embryo-like structures (Kagawa *et al.*, 2022; Liu,

557 Tan, *et al.*, 2021) provides an additional platform to assess how ODS influence early
558 developmental trajectories in a controlled and ethically regulated framework (Kagawa *et al.*,
559 2022; Shibata *et al.*, 2024). Addressing these questions will not only improve reproducibility but
560 also clarify how close we are to achieving a physiologically meaningful, translationally relevant
561 *in vitro* milieu.

562

563 **Toward more complex and physiologically accurate systems: assembloids**

564 Assembloids provide a major step forward for studying reproductive tract secretions because their
565 multicellular organization restores epithelial–stromal communication (with unprecedented *in*
566 *vitro* fidelity, Figure 2 and 3): a key driver of physiologically relevant secretome profiles,
567 including during the window of implantation (Zhang *et al.*, 2024). Unlike epithelial-only
568 organoids, human endometrial assembloids generate hormone-responsive secretions that more
569 accurately represent the transition to a receptive state. Stromal cells further contribute with
570 decidual products such as PRL, IGFBP1 and senescence-associated signals that shape the
571 composition and timing of the essential molecules for implantation (Gnecco *et al.*, 2023; Tian *et*
572 *al.*, 2023). Beyond physiological modelling, endometrial assembloids retain donor-specific
573 signatures and capture clinically relevant alterations, such as progesterone-resistant
574 endometriosis, adenomyosis and recurrent implantation failure (Rawlings *et al.*, 2021;
575 Stratopoulou *et al.*, 2025), making them highly relevant for understanding implantation failure
576 and ART outcomes.

577 Current multicompartiment assembloids (MA) are innovative constructs that remain in earlier
578 stages of development. Fallopian tube MA incorporates a basement membrane-like Matrigel core
579 containing the epithelial cells, surrounded by a collagen I-rich stromal compartment (Figure 3B),
580 recreating the epithelial-stromal organization and mucosal folding characteristic of the *in vivo*
581 fallopian tube. This architecture enhances epithelial differentiation, motile ciliation and associated
582 proteomic diversity, resulting in luminal secretions and fluid dynamics that resemble native tubal
583 physiology. Moreover, cilia developed by the fallopian tube assembloids are not only present but
584 functionally active, producing directional ciliary beating sufficient to transport oocyte-sized cargo

585 along the lumen-facing epithelial surface, recapitulating a fundamental mechanical function of
586 the fallopian tube (Crawford *et al.*, 2024).

587 A parallel effort has focused on building endometrial MAs. This platform recapitulates the
588 proliferative, secretory and menstrual regression phases within a single culture system, supports
589 decidualization, and reveals compartment-specific paracrine signaling. By uniting tissue-
590 informed design with full-cycle hormonal responsiveness, these endometrial MA establish a
591 powerful foundation for studying implantation, modeling gynecological disease, and advancing
592 precision reproductive diagnostics (Ren *et al.*, 2025).

593 Receptive endometrial scaffold platforms like the cell-engineered receptive endometrial scaffold
594 technology (Figure 4A, B), the 3D endometrioid on a chip (Figure 4C), and the 3D post-
595 implantation co-culture system (Figure 4D) are even able to model the early human embryo and
596 blastoid implantation process *in vitro*, recapitulating key post-implantation hallmarks such as yolk
597 sac formation, primordial germ cell specification, and early placental development (Dong *et al.*,
598 2025; Molè *et al.*, 2026; Song *et al.*, 2026). Crucially, these models not only advance our
599 understanding of embryo–maternal communication but also faithfully reproduce the luminal,
600 glandular and stromal compartments of the receptive endometrium (Figure 4B), providing a
601 physiologically relevant context for the study and collection of *in vitro* secretions, including those
602 involved in oviductal, endometrial and embryonic interactions (Dong *et al.*, 2025; Molè *et al.*,
603 2026; Song *et al.*, 2026). Moreover, these overcome the limitations of accessibility and ethical
604 constraints in early pregnancy research. All these features position assembloids as an intermediate
605 system between current organoid cultures, which lack complex tissue interactions, and whole-
606 uterus models, which remain experimentally constrained.

607

608 **Next-generation models of reproductive function and diseases: vascularized and immune**
609 **assembloids**

610 Future studies should integrate a more fluent communication between vascular and immune
611 components into reproductive assembloids. This way, next-generation secretomes would more
612 faithfully reflect *in vivo* uterine and oviductal fluid. Advances such as the AO-EMOs with stroma

613 and endothelium (Figure 3C) provide a blueprint for engineering reproductive assembloids in
614 which endothelial networks contribute angiocrine factors essential for receptivity, decidual
615 remodeling and early embryo support.

616 Additionally, incorporating micropatterned hydrogel scaffolds or hybrid chips with cell culture
617 inserts would further refine secretions generation by recreating tissue-specific architecture:
618 glandular invaginations in the endometrium or the folded ciliated surface of the fallopian tube,
619 both of which are analogous to how villus-crypt-mimicking interfaces enhance intestinal
620 maturation (Shin and Kim, 2022). These patterned systems would allow spatially organized
621 secretions (hormone signaling, immune-vascular-epithelial crosstalk, and embryo or trophoblast
622 interactions) under physiologically relevant mechanical and biochemical cues.

623

624 **Conclusions**

625 *In vitro* embryo development, while foundational to both human assisted reproductive
626 technologies (ART) and livestock breeding programs, continues to fall short of replicating the
627 dynamic and finely tuned environment of the female reproductive tract. Efforts to supplement
628 culture media with reproductive fluids have demonstrated improved embryo quality,
629 developmental competence, and epigenetic stability. However, practical limitations, including
630 donor variability, biosafety concerns and lack of standardization, have restricted their widespread
631 implementation.

632 Organoid-derived secretions, 3D *in vitro* culture (organoids and assembloids), scaffolds, chips,
633 and co-culture systems now offer a scalable and ethically viable alternative. These models
634 generate bioactive secretomes that closely mimic oviductal and uterine fluids, providing a
635 physiologically relevant and reproducible source of factors essential for early development. In
636 human ARTs, 3D-based platforms hold the potential to personalize embryo culture conditions,
637 reduce reliance on undefined supplements, and improve implantation and long-term
638 developmental outcomes.

639 As the field advances, the integration of organoid technologies, extracellular vesicle biology and
640 functional co-culture systems represents a transformative shift toward biomimetic embryo

641 culture. These innovations not only bridge the gap between *in vivo* and *in vitro* environments but
642 also offer translational benefits supporting safer, more effective and physiologically-informed
643 reproductive strategies in clinical settings.

644

645 **Data availability**

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647

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652

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654 V.P.-G. and P.C. conceptualized the manuscript. N.H.-D., S.N.-S., and V.P.-G. wrote the
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665

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667 None of the authors have a conflict of interest to disclose

668

669 **Figure Legends**

670

671 **Figure 1. Comparison of fertilization and early embryo development in the female**

672 **reproductive tract and in laboratory culture conditions.** The upper panel illustrates

673 fertilization and preimplantation embryo development *in vivo*, within the female reproductive

674 tract. In this physiological context, gametes and embryos are exposed to a dynamic and complex

675 microenvironment composed of follicular, oviductal and uterine fluids. These fluids contain a

676 wide range of bioactive components, including proteins, metabolites, lipids, hormones and

677 extracellular vesicles, and are influenced by epithelial secretions, fluid flow, and hormonal

678 changes. Together, these factors regulate fertilization, early embryonic development and embryo-

679 maternal communication.

680 The lower panel depicts the conventional IVF workflow, in which sperm preparation, fertilization,

681 and embryo culture are performed using static, chemically defined culture media. These systems

682 lack many of the biochemical and physical properties of the *in vivo* environment. The figure

683 highlights how supplementation with reproductive fluids, or their bioactive components, at

684 specific stages of *in vitro* culture may improve fertilization outcomes and embryo quality by more

685 closely mimicking physiological conditions. IVP, *in vitro* embryo production.

686

687 **Figure 2. Generation and structural features of endometrial organoids and assembloids**

688 **derived from reproductive tissues.** (A) Schematic representation of the female reproductive

689 tract in human and bovine species, including the ovaries, fallopian tubes (oviducts), uterus and

690 cervix. The inset highlights the endometrium, showing the luminal epithelial layer and the

691 underlying stromal compartment. (B) Overview of the generation of *in vitro* three-dimensional

692 models. Epithelial cells are isolated and embedded within an extracellular matrix scaffold to form

693 epithelial organoids. Stromal cells can be cultured separately as a monolayer or combined with

694 epithelial cells to generate multicellular epithelial-stromal assembloids that partially recapitulate

695 tissue organization. (C) Diagram of epithelial cell polarity within organoids, illustrating apical-

696 basal organization. The apical (luminal-facing) surface is oriented toward the organoid lumen,

697 while the basolateral surface interacts with the surrounding extracellular matrix. **(D)**
698 Representative morphology of epithelial organoids and epithelial-stromal assembloid-like
699 structures grown in extracellular matrix, showing three-dimensional architecture and cellular
700 organization. ECM, extracellular matrix.

701

702 **Figure 3. Approaches for generating advanced endometrial organoids and multicellular**
703 **assembloids.** **(A)** Scaffold-free three-dimensional organoids generated using agarose
704 micromoulds, containing both epithelial and stromal cell populations. The inset illustrates the
705 secretion of structural and mucosal components, including collagen, mucins and glycoproteins.
706 Immunostaining for cell-type-specific markers, such as vimentin (stromal cells) and E-cadherin
707 (epithelial cells), highlights the spatial organization of the different compartments. **(B)**
708 Multicellular assembloid model comprising a central epithelial compartment surrounded by a
709 stromal cell layer, partially recapitulating epithelial-stromal tissue architecture. **(C)** Apical-out
710 organoid configuration in which the epithelial apical (luminal) surface is oriented outward,
711 allowing direct exposure to the external environment. Insets show ciliated epithelial structures
712 and luminal organization. Cytoskeletal and polarity markers, including basal lamina components,
713 filamentous actin and acetylated α -tubulin, illustrate epithelial polarity and cellular specialization.
714 **(D)** Apical-out organoid incorporating epithelial, stromal and endothelial cell populations to
715 model epithelial-stromal-vascular interactions. Cell-type-specific markers confirm the presence
716 and organization of the three cellular compartments. AO, apical-out.

717

718 **Figure 4. Three-dimensional models for studying embryo implantation and early post-**
719 **implantation development.** **(A)** Schematic representation of a reconstructed endometrial
720 scaffold generated by layering a stromal hydrogel within a compartmentalized culture system and
721 overlaying it with organoid-derived epithelial fragments to form a luminal epithelial layer.
722 Separate culture media are used for stromal and epithelial compartments to preserve cell-specific
723 differentiation. This engineered platform recreates stromal-epithelial architecture and supports a
724 hormonally responsive endometrial environment. **(B)** Hormone-driven differentiation and

725 embryo interaction within the reconstructed endometrial model. Upper panels show epithelial
726 remodeling in response to hormonal stimulation. Under oestrogen exposure, the epithelium
727 displays a proliferative phenotype with shallow gland-like structures. Subsequent treatment with
728 progesterone and cyclic AMP induces a secretory phenotype, characterized by increased
729 glandular complexity and expression of differentiation markers. Lower panels illustrate embryo
730 or blastoid attachment and invasion, including trophoblast expansion and differentiation into
731 distinct lineages surrounding embryonic compartments. **(C)** Three-dimensional endometrial
732 implantation model within a microfluidic platform. A hormonally primed endometrial tissue is
733 assembled through sequential layering of extracellular matrix, stromal cells, glandular epithelial
734 organoids and a luminal epithelial layer. This compartmentalized system enables controlled
735 embryo attachment and invasion under dynamic culture conditions. **(D)** Three-dimensional post-
736 implantation co-culture model incorporating epithelial, stromal, immune and supporting-cell
737 populations. Organoid-derived epithelial structures are hormonally primed to mimic the receptive
738 phase of the endometrium. Embryos are introduced into a defined niche within the structure,
739 allowing modelling of key implantation processes, including attachment, epithelial penetration
740 and trophoblast differentiation, within a stabilized *in vitro* microenvironment. cAMP, cyclic
741 adenosine monophosphate; E2, oestradiol; GE, glandular epithelial organoids; LE, luminal
742 epithelial cells; mP4, medroxyprogesterone acetate; ST, stromal cells.

743

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Figure 1. Comparison of fertilization and early embryo development in the female reproductive tract and in laboratory culture conditions. The upper panel illustrates fertilization and preimplantation embryo development *in vivo*, within the female reproductive tract. In this physiological context, gametes and embryos are exposed to a dynamic and complex microenvironment composed of follicular, oviductal, and uterine fluids. These fluids contain a wide range of bioactive components, including proteins, metabolites, lipids, hormones, and extracellular vesicles, and are influenced by epithelial secretions, fluid flow, and hormonal changes. Together, these factors regulate fertilization, early embryonic development, and embryo-maternal communication.

The lower panel depicts the conventional *in vitro* fertilization (IVF) workflow, in which sperm preparation, fertilization, and embryo culture are performed using static, chemically defined culture media. These systems lack many of the biochemical and physical properties of the *in vivo* environment. The figure highlights how supplementation with reproductive fluids, or their bioactive components, at specific stages of *in vitro* culture may improve fertilization outcomes and embryo quality by more closely mimicking physiological conditions. Abbreviations: IVF, *in vitro* fertilization; IVP, *in vitro* embryo production.

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Figure 2. Generation and structural features of endometrial organoids and assembloids derived from reproductive tissues. (A) Schematic representation of the female reproductive tract in human and bovine species, including the ovaries, fallopian tubes (oviducts), uterus, and cervix. The inset highlights the endometrium, showing the luminal epithelial layer and the underlying stromal compartment. (B) Overview of the generation of *in vitro* three-dimensional models. Epithelial cells are isolated and embedded within an extracellular matrix scaffold to form epithelial organoids. Stromal cells can be cultured separately as a monolayer or combined with epithelial cells to generate multicellular epithelial-stromal assembloids that partially recapitulate tissue organization. (C) Diagram of epithelial cell polarity within organoids, illustrating apical-basal organization. The apical (luminal-facing) surface is oriented toward the organoid lumen, while the basolateral surface interacts with the surrounding extracellular matrix. (D) Representative morphology of epithelial organoids and epithelial-stromal assembloid-like structures grown in extracellular matrix, showing three-dimensional architecture and cellular organization. Abbreviations: ECM, extracellular matrix.

361x370mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 3. Approaches for generating advanced endometrial organoids and multicellular assembloids. (A) Scaffold-free three-dimensional organoids generated using agarose micromoulds, containing both epithelial and stromal cell populations. The inset illustrates the secretion of structural and mucosal components, including collagen, mucins, and glycoproteins. Immunostaining for cell-type-specific markers, such as vimentin (stromal cells) and E-cadherin (epithelial cells), highlights the spatial organization of the different compartments. (B) Multicellular assembloid model comprising a central epithelial compartment surrounded by a stromal cell layer, partially recapitulating epithelial-stromal tissue architecture. (C) Apical-out organoid configuration in which the epithelial apical (luminal) surface is oriented outward, allowing direct exposure to the external environment. Insets show ciliated epithelial structures and luminal organization. Cytoskeletal and polarity markers, including basal lamina components, filamentous actin, and acetylated α -tubulin, illustrate epithelial polarity and cellular specialization. (D) Apical-out organoid incorporating epithelial, stromal, and endothelial cell populations to model epithelial-stromal-vascular interactions. Cell-type-specific markers confirm the presence and organization of the three cellular compartments. Abbreviations: AO, apical-out.

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Figure 4. Three-dimensional models for studying embryo implantation and early post-implantation development. (A) Schematic representation of a reconstructed endometrial scaffold generated by layering a stromal hydrogel within a compartmentalized culture system and overlaying it with organoid-derived epithelial fragments to form a luminal epithelial layer. Separate culture media are used for stromal and epithelial compartments to preserve cell-specific differentiation. This engineered platform recreates stromal-epithelial architecture and supports a hormonally responsive endometrial environment. (B) Hormone-driven differentiation and embryo interaction within the reconstructed endometrial model. Upper panels show epithelial remodeling in response to hormonal stimulation. Under oestrogen exposure, the epithelium displays a proliferative phenotype with shallow gland-like structures. Subsequent treatment with progesterone and cyclic AMP induces a secretory phenotype, characterized by increased glandular complexity and expression of differentiation markers. Lower panels illustrate embryo or blastoid attachment and invasion, including trophoblast expansion and differentiation into distinct lineages surrounding embryonic compartments. (C) Three-dimensional endometrioid implantation model within a microfluidic platform. A hormonally primed endometrial tissue is assembled through sequential layering of extracellular matrix, stromal cells, glandular epithelial organoids, and a luminal epithelial layer. This compartmentalized system enables controlled embryo attachment and invasion under dynamic culture conditions. (D) Three-dimensional post-implantation co-culture model incorporating epithelial, stromal, immune, and supporting cell populations. Organoid-derived epithelial structures are hormonally primed to mimic the receptive phase of the endometrium. Embryos are introduced into a defined niche within the structure, allowing modelling of

key implantation processes, including attachment, epithelial penetration, and trophoblast differentiation within a stabilized in vitro microenvironment. Abbreviations: cAMP, cyclic adenosine monophosphate; E2, oestradiol; GE, glandular epithelial organoids; LE, luminal epithelial cells; mP4, medroxyprogesterone acetate; ST, stromal cells.

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Table 1: Composition of selected commercial in vitro embryo culture media compared with reference basal media

Brand				Fujifilm Irvine Sci.	Vitrolife	Vitrolife	Vitrolife	Cooper Surgical	Cooper Surgical	Cooper Surgical	Gynemed	FertiPro
Medium	Modified Earle's	Mouse Egg Medium	Ham's F10	CSCM-NXC	G-TL™	G-1™ PLUS	G-2™ PLUS	SAGE 1-Step™ GM-CSF	EmbryoGen®	BlastGen™	GM501 Cult with Gentamicin	GAIN™ Medium
Culture protocol				One Step	One Step	Sequential	Sequential	One Step	Sequential	Sequential	One Step	One Step
Salts												
CaCl ₂	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
KCl	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X
KH ₂ PO ₄		X									X	
MgSO ₄	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Na ₂ HPO ₄			X									X
NaCl	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
NaH ₂ PO ₄	X			X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
NaHCO ₃	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Carbohydrates												
Calcium lactate		X										X
Glucose	X	X	X	X				X	X	X	X	X
Sodium citrate	X			X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
Sodium lactate				X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Sodium pyruvate	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Amino acids & protein source												
Essential amino acids				X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Human serum albumin				X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

Hyaluronic acid				X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
Non-essential amino acids				X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Taurine									X			
Others												
EDTA				X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Vitamins				X	X		X	X	X	X		
Lipoic acid (antioxidant)				X	X	X						
Additional antioxidants				X	X		X	X	X	X		
Gentamicin (antibiotic)					X		X	X	X	X	X	X
GM-CSF (cytokine)								X	X	X		

X indicates the presence of the component in the formulation according to manufacturer descriptions. Commercial media compositions are based on publicly available information and may not reflect proprietary or undisclosed components. Culture protocols are classified as one-step (single medium throughout development) or sequential (stage-specific media). Abbreviations: CaCl₂, calcium chloride; KCl, potassium chloride; KH₂PO₄, potassium dihydrogen phosphate; MgSO₄, magnesium sulfate; Na₂HPO₄, disodium hydrogen phosphate; NaCl, sodium chloride; NaH₂PO₄, sodium dihydrogen phosphate; NaHCO₃, sodium bicarbonate; EDTA, ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid; GM-CSF, granulocyte–macrophage colony-stimulating factor.

Table 2: Concentrations of major osmolytes in human uterine fluid, serum and oviductal fluid across reproductive phases

	Uterine fluid			Serum	Oviductal fluid	Oviductal fluid	
	Proliferative phase	Mid-cycle phase	Luteal phase			Preovulatory phase	Postovulatory phase
Osmolarity (mOsm/kg)	276–307	276–298	282–302	278–302	–	–	–
K (mmol/L)	24.5–27.5	12.6–25.7	18.8–28.0	3.7–4.8	3.6–5.0	9.9±1.8	7.7±0.9
Na (mmol/L)	98–118	96–130	99–119	139–145	139–147	140±3	139±2
Ca (mmol/L)	0.41–1.98	0.21–1.69	1.01–2.49	2.29–2.85	2.27–2.72	1.89±0.52	2.37±0.27
Cl (mmol/L)	108–111	105–117	111–117	105–114	102–113	119±4	117±3

Values are reported as ranges or mean ± standard deviation, depending on the original study. Uterine fluid values correspond to different phases of the menstrual cycle (proliferative, mid-cycle, and luteal). Oviductal fluid values correspond to preovulatory and postovulatory stages. Abbreviations: Ca, calcium; Cl, chloride; K, potassium; Na, sodium; mOsm/kg, milliosmoles per kilogram. Data sources: Casslén et al. (1984); Borland et al. (1980); Lippes et al. (1972).